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Girls Not Boys: A Predictor of Culture Modification Impact on Girl's-Child Enrolment in Schools among Rural Family in Northern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Having daughters, not sons to predict the educational advantage among the rural family may be controversial in a patriarchal society. This is so, as such a societies are perceiving daughter and son from traditional gender ideology not from the human capital viewpoint. Patriarchal society feels guilty when daughters turn out to be determined, assertive, and competent than sons. For decades, the most prevailing communities' attitudes toward girls' child education in Hausa land is discouraging. Particularly, in rural areas girls often do not progress beyond the primary school level. Many farm families view their daughters' education as futile investment leading to immorality. The prevailing mind-set particularly, among semi-urban communities need to undergo a transformative shift, as the communities need to recognize the societal and economic significance of educated female in Nigeria. The hindrances that prompt families to marry off their daughters prematurely are attributed to low economic status, poverty and cultural norms with the perception that girl-child education is more costly than that of boys. These negative attitudes set backed the overall development of the society. To investigate these challenges a Nominal Group Techniques ((NGT), individual interview with key informants and observational methods were be used to conduct this study. The paper draws analysis on collected data from 216 households in Binary Logistic Regression (BLR). Triangulating the data from various sources enhances the reliability and quality of the research. It identified girls as a predictor of high school enrolments in rural northern Nigeria with $p=0.042$ and $exp(B)=3.258$. The household inter-change roles in the rural family culture may be emerges as a critical determinant.

Keywords: Girls, Predictor Culture, Girl's-Child, Enrolment, School, Rural Family, Northern Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Right, every human being must enjoy the right to social security, as recognized by the United Nations (UNICEF, 2018). In the Article 28, the Declaration stated that, "Everyone is entitled to a social security as an international order in which the rights and freedoms were set in this Declaration and must be fully realized" (UNESCO, 2019). Patriarchal as a

system of family is practice in some parts of the world, including Hausa land of northern Nigeria (Philip, 1995), where males being considered always superior and assumed position of “breadwinners” of the families (Alam, 2011). The females members of family are mostly assign the roles of taking care of the entire families (Zumilah,2010) and a such this is recognized and maintained through an intricate cultural trap of either institutions, laws, or norms and values (Abbas 2003). The female members of family have their major roles; to becomes a wives and a mothers who always stay and work at home (Aisha, & Yahuza, 2018). They were subjected to the males’ authority on any decision and control; as the only males can exercise their authority in the public and domestic spheres (Alhassan,, 2015). This system served as a rationale for favoring the boy’s education over that of girls which perpetuated more commonly in rural areas of northern Nigeria (Abdullahi, 2014). This is also a reason for decades, most families and communities attitudes toward girls’ child education in rural Hausa land is not encouraging (Philip, 1995). Cultural devaluation of girls’ education presents negative impact on their advancement in the levels of education (Abdullahi, Zainalaludin, & Paim, 2013). This might be what led to consideration of their early marriage as better option.

However, in reality these is what increase their poverty level and societal insecurity which also is an effort to deny the attainment of reasonable level of education by girls child, and will keep creating more gap in gender equality as in Abdullahi (2014). The girls-child education will continue diminishing (Bell, 2010), as long as the superior-subordination relationships of males over females exist within the families and the society at upper levels (Zumilah, 2010) This type of system rises and becomes stronger where males are prioritized and are expected to provide the needs for the entire families (Abdullahi, Zainalaludin, & Paim, 2013)., while women are to be extremely under control in the only issues related to domestic sphere (Abdullahi & Maiunguwa). These attitudes are related to the belief that, the males are more valuable than females (Abdullahi, Zumilah & Paim, 2013). They were place to bear the father’s names and equally have the traditional rights over their families (Bond, 1998). This system is rooted in rural Hausa society and affects the enrolment and retention of girls-child into the schools to the completion level of education. The system also tried down grade the economic status of females as they grown, the girls-children poverty level also raises (Adamu, 2017). The situation becomes a root causes of why families are favoring the education of their sons rather than their daughters. This at most time they cannot send both to schools, they rather married out the girls-child (Aisha, 2016), most time at the early age to other families and relieve themselves from the financial burden of educating them. Thus, there is need for education policies to look in complementing cultural practices; so that the enrolment and retention of girls-child into the education system to the completion level could be increasing for sustainable development (UNESCO, 2017).

Problem Statement

Most existing narratives and literatures related to cultural impact on the girls-child education are found in UNICEF (2015); FME, (2013); UNESCO, (2019); and other fewer related documents. However, these sources have more focus on general obstacles to girls-child attainment of western education in Africa, not specifically considering issues such as culture on the girls-child education in a specific context. The results were also found mainly from survey with small sampled data in the work which does not fully represent the reality in real scenarios (Aisha,,2016) The present research is intended to harmonize and bridge those existing gaps with the particular reference to rural Hausa land of northern Nigeria. This research aims to be a useful reference for all the states in region as they shared common futures (Wersebe, 2017) demographically. Evidently, not much has been done to explore why most school-age girls are not having equal access to schools with their counterpart boys, particularly up to the completing level of educations in most parts of these states. The findings will be a vital key towards the gender and development related issue of human civilization and as in UNESCO, (2007).reports.

Specifically, Katsina State and all other states in the region for example have girl-child education programs in one way. However, it has never been regarded as a priority investment for human development in the states. Currently most available reports on girls-child education is still showing that majority of girls have no access to schools in the northern states of Nigeria (UNICEF, 2015; UNESCO,

2019; & FME, 2013). However, why the phenomena is persisting is because is not given needed attention, therefore the scenarios reality were not much explored. This is what has necessitated the need to explore in-depth from the girls and their parents views points. Also, previous researchers focused more on regional barriers and other related issues (Abdullahi, 2014; UNICEF, 2015; UNESCO, 2019; & FME, 2013) that have to do with inefficiency on the part of the government programs on the matter, such as poor infrastructures and funding among others. This research argues that at the micro level, there is insufficient evidence to consider as the effects of deep-rooted socio-cultural factors such as street hawking, and females exclusion in the family decision making (social seclusion) among others.

Furthermore, the family arrangement, as well as societal institutions settings are always embedded with the elements of gender discrimination that lead to girl-child education being relegated to the background just by virtue of their gender (Abdullahi, Zainalaludin, & Paim, 2013). This called for the need to conduct more research to explore more reasons for the persisted practice. There is similar issue identified by Haruna and Saifullahi (2012) where they found in most communities in Katsina state, Nigeria, females have never been recognized as robust enough to make their quota contribution in the decision-making process within the family affairs. The most important decisions are taken by the males as superior folk. However, the issue is not about equating both the sexes to be same, but rather the opportunities, rights and responsibilities should be influence not by whether they are born females or males (Aklin, 2018). This standard is leading to attainment of healthier society with a view to sustainable development, as such the following specific objectives were proposed.

Objective of the Study

1. To examine the cultural factors influencing girls' enrolment and retention in school among rural and farm family in Hausa land.
2. To correlate the impact of prevailing cultural factors influencing girls education in the society of Hausa land
3. To propose recommendations for shifting societal perspective and promoting girls education in the region.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Socio-cultural learning theory viewed Societies as surrounded by many influential institutional factors, such as family, schools, teachers, parents, media and friends and larger society (Zumilah, 2010). These factors influence the outlook of masculine and feminine roles and behaviors among individuals and society. These were in everywhere either in workplaces or in other societal life spares, including the education domains. The children's enrolment, retention and completion of schools (Abdullahi, 2014), need to be inclusive. Furthermore, others family and societal practices on education may be included from time to time to encourage the gender equity and equality in education. However, liberal theory recognizes the crucial impact of cultural attitudes and policies in providing a structure for less privileged and girls-child. It argued that all people are created on equal basis and should not be denied equality of opportunity because of their gender (Aklin, et.al.. (2018). Therefore, the relevant literatures should intensified the need for increasing level of family and society awareness as critical factor in getting out gender education disparity in Hausa land of northern Nigeria. The mentality toward girl-child education particularly in rural setting can be change in the mindset of this majority populace. This is possible once the people have admired the crucial benefits of female education in their lives (Aisha, 2016). Thus the challenges that are pushing the families to denied their daughters education such as early marriage, patriarchy system are not only resulted to their poverty, but persistent ignorance which also plays a vital roles in making others (Aisha, 2016, Abdullahi, 2014 Zumilah, 2010), on girl-child education among farm family.

Early Marriage and Girl Child Education

Early marriage is common practices, particularly in the remote rural areas where they are not exposed to the dividends of females' education in their areas (Akunga, 2010). However, some families might perceive it as, no matter how they wish to educate their girls-child (Abdullahi, 2014), the situation will remain difficult, due to the locations of schools are far away from their homes. The parents have

developed fear of given exposure to their daughters, therefore, they prepared to marry them off to preserve and maintain their family name and culture (Akpan, 2012). This cultural adherent may clearly present a negative relationship between education and patriarchy (Anikina, et, al 2015) as well as positive one between early marriage and poverty as in Arifin, & Hermino, (2017). The situation was viewed as the tempering the societal security when allowed girls in the farm family to attain schools up to the completion level. This situation has rifted a greater gender inequality in education income, and other social disparity.

The gender inequality in education among farm family is not a result of girls' inability to attend schools but rather opted for early marriage in Hausa land of northern Nigeria has been visible for decades (Audu, et, al., 2006). Though the concept of early marriage has a contentious discuss among, academia within the communities with several dimensions depending on the disciplines and perception as discovered in (Audu, et, al., 2006). This is determined by people's cultures, tradition, background and religion. Thus, the legal marriageable age according to prescribed law in Nigeria is 18 years and is the same as in UNICEF (20015), which stated that early marriage takes place among spouses at the age under 18years. According to early child marriage act, which states "No person under the age of 18 years is capable of contracting a valid marriage and accordingly a marriage so contracted is null and void and of no effect whatsoever". The aforementioned act is referring to a situation whereby the children under age of 18 years may contract and arrange a marriage without consents of their parents or other adult guidance. This is same as in article 14(2) states: "State parties shall respect the rights and duties of the parents and, when applicable, legal guardians to provide direction to the child in the exercise of his or her right in a manner consistent with the evolving capacities of the child". While, the 1999 C constitution, section 38(1) stipulates that: "Every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief".

Over the past centuries there are theories that agreed with the crucial impact of culture, attitudes and policies provided by a system structure. These in most cases have a negative effect on the rural poor and less privileged girls (Aisha, 2016). The changes experienced in contemporary society stressed the argument that, all people irrespective of their gender, race and geography are created equally and should not be denied equality in any opportunity (Arifin, & Hermino,2017). Therefore, both boys and girls should be given equal opportunities in aspect of societal development these include education, economic, politics, and other activities (Haruna & Saifullahi, 2012). This theory is aligned with the provision of Nigerian constitution of 1999, that stated categorically, as a fundamental human right, every citizen should have access to free, basic and compulsory education.

Patriarchy system of Family and Girl Child Education

According to anthropologists and sociologists, patriarchy as a structure of family that allows the father or the oldest male figure in the family to exercise and enjoy the power and authority over all the members in the family. This form of family system in most farm family globally as in Zumilar, (2010,) is affecting the courage and strength of females family members to pursue education like males.. Patriarchy as a system where men are superiors and are adopting and taking the position of "breadwinners" of the families), and were women are assign the role of taking care of the entire families (Jafar, 2019). This system is recognised and Maintained through an intricate trap of institutions, laws, norms and values (Idris (2017). The female family members and their roles are to become wives and a mothers who always stay and work at home. The women are subjected to male's authority, decision and control in the system, as men exercise authority and power in the public and domestic spheres. These types of superior-subordinate relationships between men and women exist within the families and society at large.

This system go up where men are expected to provide all the financial and other needs for the entire families, while women being under control of men for domestic sphere. This is served as rationale behind favouring the boy's education over that of girls, and perpetuated more in rural areas of northern Nigeria. These attitudes are related to the belief that, the male children are more valuable than female children, because they will bear father's names and equally have the traditional rights over other their families. This notion is what guides assertion "if you educate a girl, she will misbehave, and have a feeling of not

respecting, obeying, the respected society, instead she should be married off at the tender age to avoid such behaviour". Thus, early believe is common in rural areas where they are not exposed to the dividends and value of education

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design would involve a mixed methods in nature with the qualitative and quantitative approaches (Ary, et,al, 2006, & Conboy, 2012). The qualitative specifically have a focus on key participants; street hawking Girl-Childs, and their parents in addition the policymakers. The research participants were drawn from selected Local Government Areas of the states. The data collection technique involves engaging participants in NGT where discussion on the matter using semi-structured open-ended questions (Banerjee, & Chaudhury, 2010) conducted. Observations from the secondary data were made to compare with the data collected which finally converted into figures for analysis. The raw data was sets to represent 216 households in Binary Logistic Regression (BLR), that guide identifying major themes (Fraenkel et, al., 2011) In essence, this research, utilized both primary and secondary data that was produced in triangulation manner (Barimah, 2013). The analysis using BLR on cultural factors that may be the strong factors that affect girl's enrolment and retention in schools up to the completing stage was justified.

FINDINGS

The BLR statistics obtained $p \leq 0.05$ in Omnibus Test of Model Coefficient. This indicates that the Model is significant to explain the likelihood of high girls-child enrolment in school when the cultural factors were controled. Hosmer and Lemeshow test of goodness of fit statistic at $p > 0.05$, indicates the predictor variables in the Model were linearly related to log odds of high girls-child enrolment. This also showed the Model variables were sufficient and fit to predict the likelihood high girls-child enrolment. The model was constructed as a Family Background Model (FBM), comprising six (6) variables. The variables are years in marriage, education level, source of income, presence of boy (son) in school, presence of girl (daughter) in school and age of school entry. From these variables, three are on scales data while the remaining are on categorical data. The variable components were significantly ($p < 0.05$) predicted high girls-child enrolment in the Model. Therefore, it was concluded that FBM was significant to predict the likelihood of high girls-child enrolment while the cultural factors were in control. Hence, FBM rejected H_0 , that there exist no family background variables predicted the likelihood of high-girls child enrolment in school under control of other factors. The below was an equation of the Model.

$$Z_2 = -0.809 + 1.049 + 0.787 + 2.522 - 0.215 + 1.181 + 0.937 + 0.697 + 0.454 + -0.886 + -1.391 + 0.001 + 0.687 + 1.692 + 1.941 - 0.164$$

Equation: Family Background Model

The paper reported all the significant variables components; however, the discussion was focus only on the presence of girls (daughter) in school as a predictor of high girls-child enrolment in school in FBM. The significant variables were in two types: categorical, that are *primary, secondary and tertiary education levels, presence of daughters, animal husbandry, processed food occupation and family income as well as 4-years and 5-years school entry age*. There is a scale significant variable as the *number of years in marriage* as all presented in the Model Table 1 below.

Table 1: FBM; Wald Chi-Square Statistics of Model; Dependent Variable=1

Family Background Model(FBM) n=216	B	S.E.	Wald	d.f.	Sig.	Exp(B)
FPEL	1.049	0.558	3.538	1	0.050	2.567
FSEL	0.787	0.470	2.811	1	0.049	2.861
FTEL	2.522	1.144	4.862	1	0.027	12.450
FYIM	-0.215	.049	19.531	1	0.000	0.806
FPDS	1.181	0.581	4.131	1	0.042	3.258
FMDS	0.937	0.574	2.667	1	0.012	2.552
FPSS	0.697	1.53	0.207	1	0.649	2.007
FMSS	0.454	1.513	0.07	1	0.792	1.491
FAHO	-0.886	0.399	4.946	1	0.026	0.412
FFPO	-1.391	0.492	8.000	1	0.005	0.249
FMMI	0.001	0.000	8.462	1	0.004	1.000
F3SE	0.687	0.467	2.168	1	0.141	1.988
F4SE	1.692	0.661	6.561	1	0.010	5.431
F5SE	1.941	0.477	16.586	1	0.000	6.963
F6SE	-0.164	0.518	0.101	1	0.751	0.848
CONSTANT	-0.809	2.15	0.142	1	0.707	0.445

Notes The **bolded** variables of the model were significant predictors. **FPEL= Family Pri. Educ. level, FSEL= Family Sec. Educ. Level, FTEL=Tertiary Educ. Level, FYIM= Family Years in Marriage, FPDS=Family Present of daughter in School FMDS =Family with Many Daughters in School, FPSS= Family Present of Son in School, FMSS= Family with many Son in school, FAHO=Animal Husbandry Occupation, FFPO=Family Food Processing Occupation, FMMI= Monthly income, TYSE= 3-Year School entry, F4SE= Family 4-Year School entry, F5SE=5-Years School entry, F6SE=Family 6-Year Sch entry,**

From the above finding in the Family Background Model (FBM) the education levels of family significantly predicted the likelihood of high girls-child enrolment in school in Wald Chi-Square statistic of the Model. In the comparison of primary education level (PEL) with the tertiary education level (TEL), the TEL had 12.5 times (odds=12.45) more likelihood of high girls-child enrolment in the school. By implication, this result means the family with more people or with parents who attended tertiary education level would have 12.5 times more likely to enroll their daughters in school than those with PEL.

The Model had presented a unique and interesting finding, indicating presence of daughters in school which significantly predicted the likelihood of high girl-child enrolment in school. The Wald Chi-Square statistic on the presence of daughters in school was $p < 0.05$ in the Model, with 3.3 times (odd=3.258) more likelihood of girls-child enrolment in school. However, the presence of more daughters in the school also proved the likelihood of high more girls-child enrolment in school. This implies that having many daughter enrolled in school from same family increase the chances of continue enrolling them in the next school the by parents to the completion level. The wonder of this finding is that the presence of son (boy) at any number ifrom the same family were not significant to predict or influence the girls-child enrolment in school. In addition, the age of school entry have also significantly predicted the likelihood of high girls-child enrolment in school as in the Wald Chi-Square statistic in FBM. In comparison, the three-year, four year, five-year and six year school entry age, only four and five years school entry age are significant with 5.4 time (odd 5.431) and 6.0 times (odds=6-963) with more likelihood of enrolling girls-child in school among the family of Hausa land households. However, three years and six year school entry for children is not significant to predict more likelihood of girls-child enrolment in school. The family income dad also significantly predicted the less likelihood of girls-child enrolment in school with (odds=1.000).

On the other hand, the animal husbandry and processed food business as the components of households' secondary sources of income significantly predicted less likelihood of enrolling girls-child in school. Animal husbandry had reduced the likelihood of girls-child enrolment in school by 41% with (odds=0.412 with negative *B*). Furthermore, the processed food business had reduced the likelihood of girls-child enrolment in school by 25% (odds=0.249 with negative *B*). The number of years in marriage has also significantly predicted the less likelihood of girls-child in school by 81% (odds=0.81 negative *B*). However, remaining variables in the Model were not significant in predicting the likelihood of enrolling girls-child in school as depicted in the Model table above.

The most exceptional outcome from the findings in the Model of this study was having a daughter or more, in school was appeared significant in prediction of more enrolment of girls-child school. The finding was the fulcrum of this study and it can be a baseline of its periodical continuity within the rural communities. This would support the current global trends seeking to remove any gender barriers and shift the mindset to always think toward gender equality and gender. The target here is to shift from gender equality to focus more on providing men and women with equal opportunities in the legal frameworks. However, gender equity would work to correct the historical harms that have left women behind through societal restrictions on various opportunities including education. Gender equity may also provide women with the tools to succeed through education program that offers them with various opportunities such as conditional cash transfers. The strong focus on gender equity may on short term bridges the inequality gaps by the provision of laws and policies on gender-focused programs that not only labeled the playing ground but also work to change the cultural setting as well as give more supports to women and girls-child to be educated. This cultural shift requires efforts from all stakeholders particularly the community members. Therefore, the paradigm shift to understand the differences between gender equity and equality is essential in providing supports to girls-child for schooling. This is not just by offering them the same opportunities with men but recognizing the lingering barriers that prevent those opportunities from becoming reality for countless number girls-child and young females.

The research provides both qualitative and quantitative explanations of the influence of socio-cultural modification effects on girl-child education in the northern states of Hausa land. Some of these states are already regarded as the educationally disadvantaged state in Nigeria. The girl-child may not be so lucky to be educated due to certain socio-cultural values which put them at high risk of falling into exploitation, and violation of their rights. Indeed, under such conditions of abuse and neglect, the girls-child education has symbolized the reality of all forms of discrimination in these states. However, the girls-child education is growing and is expected to grow as good wives, and mothers in their future. The study explore the effect of cultural modification on girls-child education in many families. This in family decision making is vital, particularly regarding girl-child education attainment. The Literature review of the study also provides how early marriage persisted among family with girl-child

Having a daughter or two in this study is an imperative finding though, it may seem a controversial issue to the conservative individuals, but it is as well merit in all the developed community. Although rural areas of the northern states occupied large area with patriarchal society with 100% controlled by males. The patriarchal way of life in rural society was described by Zumilah, (2010), it reduces the quality of sons' human capital in rural Malaysia. In such a society where the human capital quality of sons was reduced, the traditional gender perspective may view the human capital of daughters on the other hand, in a total dangerous position. This is because the sons in a patriarchal system have the choice of increasing their human capital quality (Shirin and Kihara 2013), through academic achievement (Abdullahi et al., 2013; Zumilah, 2010). However, the traditional gender ideology perspective of rural society in Hausa land constrained daughters from having such a choice. From this perspective, the ideology of majority in rural areas contributed to the debate on less importance of daughters' education. The issue may have similarity but differs from what (Zumilah 2010) discovered on having "sons as an issue" in Malaysian rural society. Her finding indicates that having sons is a problem to rural enterprise development among rural Malay family. This is entirely opposite case as it appeared in the rural setting of the Hausa land of northern Nigeria. However, historically rural society at large in northern Nigeria view daughters as helpers in the

households chores (Aisha, 2016). Also, others view daughters as an additional burden in households and not like sons, the daughters at one time will marry to another household but leaving out some responsibility of her with her family. Their notion was that the daughter at all-time need support from her family, even when she was finally married out to another family(Ibrahim, 2014).This type of situation can negatively affect young females and girls' education in such a society, this confirm the need for certain intervention.. This is because females' education even with an intervention, influences not only future education of girls and young females generation but the entire society (Abdullahi et al., 2013; Aisha, 2016; Aisha & Yahuza, 2018). However, most of the rural parents including the females were wishing to have sons especially firstborn who will be ambitious and can provide some supports to the family. The parents also believe that daughters are not future responsible for general supports of the family as their sons used to be. The said finding from this study contradicted any notion that traces its based origin from traditional gender ideology. However, was supported being in line with (Roe and Morris 2004) on capabilities of women in the alternative model of responsibility, and also in supports of family by (Zainalaludin, Jamaluddin, and Abd Shukor 2017). Unfortunately, these works discovered that most services established to support and protect families have been problematic, contradictory and unhelpful for mothers and daughters.

The presence of daughters in this study is an added advantage in households being a significant predictor of the likelihood of enrolling girls-child in school. This is because there is a program as a support service which empowers more female parents with employment opportunity than male parents. Thus, in the long term, would facilitate not only the development of the rural family but also the larger society and nation at large. This finding may be linked to the current intervention of girls' education empowerment program (GEEP) in the study area, in which most female parents acquire Nation Certificate in Education (NCE) as high educational qualification. The daughters being with their educated mothers even in the case of divorce or fathers' death (Abdullahi et al., 2013; Aisha, 2016; Ibrahim, 2014; Sarki, 2015), will continue schooling under their mother's supports. This is a new gender paradigm shift and conversation for most males that their stereotypes are becoming more common for females and accepted in society. This might not be unconnected to the presence of daughters in school as a predictor of the likelihood of more girls-child enrolment in school not the sons' presence. Another reason that may highlight this finding was being daughters more transformational in leadership style (Zainalaludin, Jamaluddin, and Abd Shukor 2017), and more relationship-oriented in the management (Zumilah 2010). While the sons mostly portray the opposite, they are growth-oriented, reckless in opportunity and wild in taking power and leadership(Zainalaludin, Jamaluddin, and Abd Shukor 2017) from their male parents.

In the rural area of Hausa land of northern Nigeria this finding may seem in controversies as a new gender paradigm shift. This study observes some female-headed households also a new gender paradigm shift in the Hausa land region, as it is not common after death or divorce, for a woman to stay alone with her children(Abdullahi 2013). However, this issue might not be unconnected with the presence of the mass killing of rural males by bandits and gangsters and leaving females as widows with several children (Audu, Yahya, and Bassi 2006; Olotuah and Olotuah 2016; Izugbara and Ezeh 2010; Munro et al. 2011; Pierce 2007; Sarki 2015).What was usually known, the children and female parents in the event of death or divorce will remain under the custody of fathers' family or relatives (Sarki 2015). This is generally obvious as there were concerns and generosity over females and children especially daughters by society for the lost their husbands and parents.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

Conclusion of this paper was that, having daughters not sons among rural households as a significant predictor of more girls-child enrolment in school portrayed a greater break through. It is a revolutionary process in eroding traditional gender role cluster and social gender-based stratification which rooted in the life of rural society of Hausa land of northern Nigeria. This was very clear by indicating the daughters instead of sons as a predictor of the positive likelihood of more girls-child in school which give light for the future girls' generation education. This also indicates that the traditional gender roles ideology can

gradually change if the practices of the patriarchal system were kept corroding and rusting. The gender and development efforts particularly, through education and further researches, may positively increase the human capital quality of future mothers and daughters. This was very possible when policies and more studies were embedded continuously. Improving gender education and indiscriminate in indigenous knowledge and skills as well as entrepreneurial skills such as that of cooking, handcrafting, and weaving among others will be given to all children will be very vital. This may also improve the households' family democratic setting and attainment to the tertiary level of education. The system would change to become more rational in decision making, more democratic in the household and the society at large. These may also result in the acceptance of new ideas, practices, programs and systems for gendered sustainable development. The study was limited to a single culture of rural northern Nigeria, more studies with a similar variable need to be conducted using a multicultural perspective. A longitudinal study in future is required to ascertain the existence of the development over time.

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